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**Die Bedeutung von Grasland und Futterbau in einer
nachhaltigen Landwirtschaft**

**L’importance des prairies et de la production fourragère dans
une agriculture durable**

**The importance of grassland and forage production in
sustainable agriculture**

**Schweiz. Gesellschaft für
Pflanzenbauwissenschaften SGPW-SSA**

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Die Bedeutung von Grasland und Futterbau in einer nachhaltigen Landwirtschaft

Grasland und Futterbau sind zentrale Bestandteile einer nachhaltigen Landwirtschaft – insbesondere in der Schweiz, wo sie die Grundlage der tierischen Produktion bilden und vielfältige ökologische Leistungen erbringen. Die Tagung widmet sich aktuellen wissenschaftlichen Erkenntnissen, Herausforderungen und Lösungsansätzen rund um die Nutzung, Erhaltung und Weiterentwicklung von Graslandsystemen. Im Fokus stehen Fragen der Produktivität, Biodiversität, Tiergesundheit, Landschaftsplanung und Ernährungssicherheit im Kontext des Klimawandels und wirtschaftlicher Zwänge. Der Futterbau in der Schweiz zeichnet sich im europäischen Vergleich aus durch einen hohen Flächenanteil und eine weitgehend grasbasierte Fütterung der Rauhuterverzehrer. Das Konzept der abgestuften Bewirtschaftungsintensität im Naturfutterbau erlaubt es sowohl produktionsorientierten als auch ökologischen Ziele zu erreichen. Im Kunstfutterbau nutzen die Klee-Gras-Mischungen die funktionelle Diversität zur Produktion von Futter bester Qualität. Gleichzeitig sind sie unverzichtbares Rückgrat gesunder Fruchtfolgen und der Nutzung der symbiotischen Stickstofffixierung für Futter- und Ackerbau. In alpinen Regionen zeigt der Bergfutterbau, wie landwirtschaftliche Nutzung und Naturschutz miteinander verbunden werden können: Durch extensive Bewirtschaftung werden nicht nur Lebensmittel erzeugt, sondern auch Kulturlandschaften erhalten und Erosionsschutz gewährleistet. Gleichzeitig sind historisch gewachsene Graslandschaften durch Nutzungsdruck und Flächenverlust bedroht – ihre Wiederherstellung und Vernetzung sind zentrale Aufgaben moderner Agrarpolitik. Naturnahe Graslandschaften gelten als Hotspots der Biodiversität. Die Wechselwirkungen zwischen Wildpflanzen, Insekten und Bodenorganismen sind entscheidend für die Stabilität von Agrarökosystemen. Innovative Ansaatmethoden können die Artenvielfalt degradierter Wiesen gezielt erhöhen. Auch die Züchtung von Futterpflanzen steht vor komplexen Herausforderungen: Klimaanpassung, Ertragssteigerung und Krankheitsresistenz müssen mit dem Erhalt genetischer Ressourcen in Einklang gebracht werden. Die Qualität des Graslands beeinflusst direkt die Gesundheit und das Wohlbefinden von Nutztieren. Hochwertiges Futter stärkt das Immunsystem und reduziert den Medikamenteneinsatz. Schließlich bietet die graslandbasierte Fütterung von Wiederkäuern eine Möglichkeit, Proteine effizient zu erzeugen, ohne mit dem Ackerbau für die menschliche Ernährung in Konkurrenz zu treten – und leistet damit einen Beitrag zur Ernährungssicherheit und zur Reduktion von Treibhausgasemissionen.

L'importance des prairies et de la production fourragère dans une agriculture durable

Les prairies et la culture fourragère sont des éléments centraux d'une agriculture durable, en particulier en Suisse, où elles constituent la base de la production animale et fournissent de multiples prestations écologiques. La conférence est consacrée aux connaissances scientifiques actuelles, aux défis et aux solutions possibles en matière d'utilisation, de préservation et de développement des systèmes de prairies. L'accent est mis sur les questions de productivité, de biodiversité, de santé animale, d'aménagement du paysage et de sécurité alimentaire dans le contexte du changement climatique et des contraintes économiques. En comparaison européenne, la culture fourragère en Suisse se caractérise par une forte proportion de surfaces et une alimentation largement basée sur l'herbe pour les animaux consommant du fourrage grossier. Le concept d'intensité d'exploitation graduée dans la production fourragère naturelle permet d'atteindre à la fois des objectifs de production et des objectifs écologiques. Dans la production fourragère artificielle, les mélanges de trèfle et d'herbe utilisent la diversité fonctionnelle pour produire un fourrage de la meilleure qualité. En même temps, ils constituent l'épine dorsale indispensable à une rotation saine des cultures et à l'utilisation de la fixation symbiotique de l'azote pour l'alimentation animale et l'agriculture. Dans les régions alpines, la production fourragère de montagne montre comment l'exploitation agricole et la protection de la nature peuvent être combinées : l'exploitation extensive permet non seulement de produire des denrées alimentaires, mais aussi de préserver les paysages culturels et d'assurer la protection contre l'érosion. Dans le même temps, les prairies historiques sont menacées par la pression de l'exploitation et la perte de terres – leur restauration et leur mise en réseau sont des tâches centrales de la politique agricole moderne. Les prairies semi-naturelles sont considérées comme des hauts lieux de la biodiversité. Les interactions entre les plantes sauvages, les insectes et les organismes du sol sont déterminantes pour la stabilité des écosystèmes agricoles. Des méthodes de semis innovantes peuvent augmenter de manière ciblée la biodiversité des prairies dégradées. La culture de plantes fourragères est également confrontée à des défis complexes : l'adaptation au climat, l'augmentation des rendements et la résistance aux maladies doivent être conciliées avec la préservation des ressources génétiques. La qualité des prairies a une influence directe sur la santé et le bien-être des animaux d'élevage. Un fourrage de haute qualité renforce le système immunitaire et réduit l'utilisation de médicaments. Enfin, l'alimentation des ruminants à base de prairies offre la possibilité de produire efficacement des protéines sans entrer en concurrence avec l'agriculture destinée à l'alimentation humaine, contribuant ainsi à la sécurité alimentaire et à la réduction des émissions de gaz à

effet de serre.

The importance of grassland and forage production in sustainable agriculture

Grassland and forage production are central components of sustainable agriculture – especially in Switzerland, where they form the basis of animal production and provide a wide range of ecological services. The conference will focus on current scientific findings, challenges and solutions relating to the use, conservation and further development of grassland systems. The focus is on issues of productivity, biodiversity, animal health, landscape planning and food security in the context of climate change and economic constraints. Compared to other European countries, forage production in Switzerland is characterised by a high proportion of land and a largely grass-based diet for roughage consumers. The concept of graduated management intensity in natural fodder production allows both production-oriented and ecological goals to be achieved. In temporary grasslands, clover-grass mixtures use functional diversity to produce top-quality fodder. At the same time, they are an indispensable backbone of healthy crop rotations and the use of symbiotic nitrogen fixation for fodder and arable farming. In alpine regions, mountain forage production shows how agricultural use and nature conservation can be combined: extensive farming not only produces food, but also preserves cultural landscapes and ensures erosion control. At the same time, historically developed grasslands are threatened by pressure from use and loss of land – their restoration and networking are central tasks of modern agricultural policy. Semi-natural grasslands are considered hotspots of biodiversity. The interactions between wild plants, insects and soil organisms are crucial for the stability of agricultural ecosystems. Innovative sowing methods can specifically increase the biodiversity of degraded meadows. The breeding of fodder plants also faces complex challenges: climate adaptation, yield increases and disease resistance must be reconciled with the conservation of genetic resources. The quality of grassland directly influences the health and well-being of farm animals. High-quality feed strengthens the immune system and reduces the use of medication. Finally, grassland-based feeding of ruminants offers a way to produce protein efficiently without competing with arable farming for human consumption, thereby contributing to food security and reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

Programm - Programme - Program

08:45 - 09:55 **Registrierung und Kaffee - Enregistrement et café - Registration and coffee**

09:15 - 09:55 **Generalversammlung SGPW-SSA - Assemblée générale SGPW-SSA - General assembly SGPW-SSA**

09:55 - 10:00 **Eröffnung wissenschaftliche Tagung - Ouverture de la réunion scientifique - Opening of the scientific meeting** (Katja Jacot, Agroscope)

Übersichtsreferat - Exposé général - Keynote

10:00 - 10:35 **Grassland systems as the foundation of a multifunctional Swiss agriculture** (Andreas Lüscher & Olivier Huguenin, Agroscope)

Vorträge - Présentation - Presentations I (Katja Jacot)

10:35 - 11:00 **Beyond the borders: Sustainable intensification of tropical pastures through integration of legumes and grasses with biological nitrification inhibition** Astrid Oberson Dräyer, ETH Zürich

Aktuelle Forschungsprojekte - Projets de recherche actuels - Current research projects I (Roland Kölliker)

11:00 - 11:15 **Flashpräsentationen à 3 Min. - Présentations flash de 3 min. - Flash presentations of 3 min.**

1. *Restoring alpine pastures: the impact of highland cattle on *Alnus viridis* encroachment* (Lucia S. Mochi, Agroscope)
2. *Selecting study areas representative for the highly diverse growth conditions in the Swiss summering zone* (Sarina Danioth, Agroscope / ETH Zurich)
3. *Multispecies mixtures enhance yield and trampling resistance* (Olivier Huguenin-Elie, Agroscope)
4. *Formulation and testing of a nutrient solution derived from organic waste to support hydroponic lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* 'Frilice') production for space applications* (Iciar Giménez de Azcárate, ETH Zürich)
5. *Nitrogen sources used by tropical forages in the Amazon forest margins under low input management: A 15N study* (Daniel M. Villegas)

11:15 - 11:35 **Pause - Pause - Break**

Vorträge - Présentation - Presentations II (Katja Jacot)

11:35 - 12:00 **Learnings from ten years of biodiversity monitoring in grassland-dominated agricultural landscapes of Switzerland** (Eliane Meier & Chantal Herzog, Agroscope)

12:00 - 12:25 **Restoring plant and insect diversity in lowland grasslands using different seed addition methods** (Jean-Yves Humbert, University of Bern)

Aktuelle Forschungsprojekte - Projets de recherche actuels - Current research projects II (Roland Kölliker)

12:25 - 13:00 **Flashpräsentationen à 3 Min. - Présentations flash de 3 min. - Flash presentations of 3 min.**

6. *Conservation pest control in sugar beet? A PhD project in its last steps* (Angela Studer, Agroscope)
7. *Impacts of organic fertilisation strategies on grassland soil organic carbon stocks: A case-study from Grisons* (Elisabeth Tanner, Agroscope)
8. *Bastard-Raigras verbessert die botanische Qualität von Gras-Klee-Mischungen* (Daniel Suter, Agroscope)
9. *Can soil amendments improve phosphorus (P) use efficiency of crops grown on oxidized acid sulfate soils with contrasting soil P availability* (Nhiem Nguyen, ETH Zurich)
10. *Improving the improvement program: Optimizing fodder plant breeding strategies with stochastic simulations* (Daniel Ariza Suarez, ETH Zurich)
11. *Extensification des prairies de montagne - entre rendement et biodiversité* (Isabelle Arnold, University of Bern)
12. *Biodiversity payments sustain grassland plant diversity, whereas abandonment leads to loss* (Marco Barandun, Agroscope / University of Zurich)
13. *Genetic diversity monitoring: unravelling dynamics in species and cultivar compositions in grassland* (Damian Käch, ETH Zurich / BFH-HAFL)
14. *From sequence to cross-compatibility prediction: A functional analysis of self-incompatibility haplotypes in forage grasses* (Daniela Kupper, ETH Zurich)

15. *Symactiv Pellets: A biostimulant in which biology is the main driver of soil health.* (Hassan Mustapha, Symactiv)
16. *Quelle fréquence optimale de prairies temporaires dans la rotation pour maintenir la qualité des sols agricoles?* (Thomas Guillaume, Agroscope)

13:00 - 14:15 **Lunch und Posterausstellung - Lunch et exposition des posters - Lunch and poster exhibition**

Vorträge - Présentation - Presentations II (Séverine Gabioud)

14:15 - 14:40 **Fodder crop breeding: innovation for the future** (Christoph Grieder & Michelle Nay, Agroscope)

14:40 - 15:05 **Where agriculture preserves nature: mountain forage systems between use and conservation** (Manuel Schneider & Caren Pauler)

15:05 - 15:10 **Prämierung Flashtalks - Prix des flash talks - Flash talk awards**

15:10 - 15:20 **Kurze Pause - Petite pause - Short break**

Vorträge - Présentation - Presentations III (Lea Frey)

15:20 - 15:45 **The importance of grassland and forage production for animal husbandry and animal health** (Florian Leiber, FIBL)

15:45 - 16:10 **Net human-edible protein yield and greenhouse gas emissions of grass-based dairy production** (Sebastian Ineichen & Beat Reidy, HAFL)

16:10 - 16:15 **Ende der Tagung - Fin de la réunion - End of meeting**

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Übersichtsreferate - Exposés généreaux - Keynotes

Grassland systems as the foundation of a multifunctional Swiss agriculture

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The predominance of grassland in Switzerland can largely be explained by the prevailing site conditions (pedoclimatic conditions, topography, precipitation patterns), which are often difficult for arable farming but favourable for grass growth. With 4/5 of its land used for agriculture being grassland, Switzerland has the second-largest proportion of grassland in Europe. This directly results in a great responsibility for the land and the fact that, of all agricultural systems, grassland is the one that covers by far the greatest gradient of site conditions, from the most favourable locations to marginal sites.

As for agriculture as a whole, the challenges for grassland-ruminant systems are diverse, complex, and interconnected. The presentation will address the seven key challenges: (1) nutrient management and efficiency, (2) biodiversity, (3) the conflict between production and ecology, (4) climate change, (5) competition for food and land, (6) maintaining soil fertility, and (7) maintaining the link between animal production and grassland.

In order to make a significant contribution to addressing these challenges, the following requirements must be met by grassland-ruminant systems: they should (1) be based on forage grown on the own farm, (2) be adapted to local site conditions, which is a challenge given their enormous range, (3) use as little concentrated feeds as possible, (4) cover the entire spectrum of management intensities in order to exploit the great potential for multifunctionality of ecosystem services, (5) continuously adapt to changing conditions, (6) be integrated into arable farming, and (7) build bridges between regions.

Current results show that forage production and grassland systems provide a wide range of ecosystem services, i.e., they are multifunctional, and that Switzerland's strategy has developed and implemented leading concepts in international comparison. In addition, opportunities for improvement are identified.

Beyond the borders: Sustainable intensification of tropical pastures through integration of legumes and grasses with biological nitrification inhibition

Astrid Oberson¹, Lorenz Allemann², Jacobo Arango³, Emmanuel Frossard¹, Olivier Huguenin-Elie⁴, Idupulapati M. Rao³, Mauricio Sotelo^{3,5,6}, Eduardo Vázquez⁵, Jaime E. Velásquez⁶, Daniel M. Villegas¹

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Large areas of tropical savanna and forest margin ecosystems in South America have been converted into pastures, typically grass monocultures without nitrogen (N) fertilization. This pattern is common in the northwestern Amazon, where grass-alone systems progressively lose productivity as soil nutrients decline, leading to widespread pasture degradation with serious ecological and economic consequences.

To explore alternatives, we assessed how integrating tropical forage legumes with grasses differing in biological nitrification inhibition (BNI) capacity influences N cycling in pasture systems. The study was conducted on smallholder farms in Caquetá, Colombia, in pastures maintained for 5–30 years with either low or high BNI grasses, grown alone or with a legume, on acidic, low fertility soils. We quantified forage biomass, plant N uptake, biological N₂ fixation, and key soil N pools and fluxes.

Legume presence and grass species both strongly affected the soil–plant N cycle. Grass–legume pastures with high BNI grasses produced higher forage yields than grass-alone pastures, and soils under grass–legume mixtures contained more mineral N. This was likely due to N₂ fixation, with legumes deriving over 70% of their N from the atmosphere. Net nitrification tended to be lower under high BNI grasses, suggesting reduced risks of nitrate leaching and nitrous oxide emissions. This is the first study to examine high BNI grasses under low input farming conditions combined with legumes to mitigate N deficiency. Our findings highlight a pathway towards sustainable intensification through biological interventions, with potential to reduce soil degradation and harmful N losses across wide areas of tropical pastures.

Learnings from ten years of biodiversity monitoring in grassland-dominated agricultural landscapes of Switzerland

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Grasslands make up the largest proportion of agricultural landscapes, covering around one-third of Switzerland and harboring a wide variety of habitats and species. However, species richness has declined largely over the past century. Recent analyses of historical vegetation records from the SNF “Square Foot Project” indicate that grasslands were much more diverse 100 years ago. The decrease was especially pronounced in lowland areas, which had substantially lower nutrient indicator values than they do today. This decline is concerning not only from a biodiversity conservation perspective, but also because biodiversity plays an important role in sustaining agricultural production through processes such as pollination and pest control.

Since 2015, the national monitoring program for agricultural species and habitats (ALL-EMA, www.allema.ch) has been systematically assessing biodiversity in Swiss agricultural landscapes. This includes evaluating the effectiveness of measures designed to promote biodiversity. In 2024, ALL-EMA completed its second five-year survey round, enabling the first assessment of changes in biodiversity over time.

In the grasslands of the valley zone, the local diversity of species targeted by the Swiss Agricultural Related Environmental Objectives increased from the first to the second survey round, while the nutrient indicator value decreased.

Ecological focus areas (EFAs) were generally effective in promoting biodiversity within these areas. However, there was no overall increase in biodiversity at the scale of entire agricultural landscapes. To achieve broader increases in biodiversity across regions, elevations and outside EFAs, more effective agri-environmental strategies are required. The third ALL-EMA survey round is underway and will provide further valuable insights into the development of biodiversity in agricultural landscapes, particularly considering changing environmental conditions and evolving policy frameworks.

Restoring plant and insect diversity in lowland grasslands using different seed addition methods

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We experimentally tested the effectiveness of different assisted restoration methods to enhance plant and invertebrate biodiversity in relatively species-poor, extensively managed Swiss lowland meadows. In 2019, four restoration treatments and a control were randomly established at field scale and replicated 12 times across the Swiss Plateau: (1) hay transfer from a species-rich donor meadow to a harrowed receiver meadow; (2) hay transfer to a ploughed meadow; (3) sowing a directly harvested native seed mixture originating from a species-rich donor meadow to a ploughed meadow; (4) sowing a propagated native mixture on a ploughed meadow; and (5) an untreated control with no soil disturbance or reseeded. Following a strong initial response in 2021, plant species richness stabilized by 2023 in most treatments, with restored meadows harbouring on average 29% more species than before restoration and 16% more species than control meadows in 2023. Hay transfer treatments increased regional beta diversity, while harrowing prior to sowing proved as effective as ploughing. Importantly, in 2023, 90% of restored meadows qualified for the result-based payment scheme (quality II), compared to none before restoration. Wild bees and butterflies showed positive responses to restoration, although not consistently across treatments, whereas hoverflies and other invertebrate groups showed no response. Overall, this real-scale study provides evidence-based recommendations for practical and financially viable grassland restoration. It also highlights that increasing plant diversity alone is insufficient, and that additional targeted actions are needed to effectively restore grassland invertebrate communities.

Fodder crop breeding: innovation for the future

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The aim of the fodder plant breeding programme at Agroscope is to develop high-yielding varieties that are adapted to local conditions and make efficient use of resources to produce high-quality forage. Thanks to the wide range of grass and legume species that are bred, Swiss forage producers have access to highly productive varieties. When used in grass-legume mixtures, these varieties contribute to a resilient and diverse production system and enable efficient, species-appropriate feeding of ruminants with a high proportion of roughage in their rations.

All the species bred by Agroscope are strictly outcrossing with a genetic self-incompatibility system and are developed as population varieties. The high genetic diversity within population varieties means they can react more flexibly to different environmental conditions, thus exhibiting greater resilience. However, the selection progress achieved in population breeding has been lower than in hybrid or line breeding. This has many reasons, among others the need to select several superior individuals to constitute a new population variety, the low observed correlation between performance of individual plants and swards, and the trade-off between seed and biomass yield in fodder plants.

Changing environmental conditions pose new challenges for forage production and fodder plant breeding. Due to the long time from first crosses in the nursery to market introduction of a variety, it is unlikely that the selection under current ambient growing conditions will be sufficient to cope with the rapidly changing climatic conditions. To meet future requirements, it is therefore necessary to anticipate, which traits will be important in the future, and to find ways to increase breeding progress for these traits. Furthermore, the range of species being worked on should be reviewed and adapted if necessary.

Tolerance to heat and drought are traits that will, obviously, play a more important role in a warming climate. To ensure forage production under drought, two strategies can be employed. A first strategy consists of improving the drought tolerance of species that are already highly digestible and adapted to Swiss agriculture, such as ryegrasses. Alternatively, species that are already drought-tolerant, such as tall fescue, orchard grass or alfalfa, can be better adapted to the requirements of Swiss forage production. The success of a selection trial on individual Italian ryegrass plants for drought tolerance over three generations in a rainout shelter was only limited. This suggests that adapting already tolerant species, i.e. by primarily improving forage quality, seems to be a more promising approach. Digestibility in the Agroscope breeding pool of cocksfoot and tall

fescue could already be noticeably improved, thereby reducing the loss of forage quality in mixtures with these species compared to pure ryegrass mixtures. Important prerequisites are efficient methods for determining forage quality parameters, above all near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS). While NIRS is already being used successfully on dried samples in the laboratory, its direct use on living plants in the field, as tested in populations of tall fescue at Agroscope, is proving more difficult.

Climate change is also influencing the emergence of new diseases that were previously more common in southern regions. For example, Southern Anthracnose caused by the fungus *Colletotrichum trifolii* has become a major threat to clover and alfalfa north of the Alps since the 1990s. Fortunately, artificial inoculation of young plants makes phenotypic selection very easy as susceptible plants die. Consistent screening of breeding populations has greatly improved the resistance level of new varieties. Similarly, stem rust caused by the fungus *Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *graminicola* is increasingly observed and causes reduced seed yield in grasses. Disease symptoms mainly appear during seed ripening, after selections have been made, making it difficult to phenotypically select for resistance. To select resistant plants before seed set, we have identified genetic markers associated with resistance to stem rust that will be validated for their use in marker-assisted selection (MAS). MAS is a suitable tool to achieving breeding progress for traits that are difficult to detect phenotypically and/or only appear late in plant development.

Increasing breeding progress for an ever-growing number of traits at the same time will be crucial in the future. Genomic selection, which is already being used successfully in animal breeding and other crops, is expected to play a decisive role in this regard. It allows prediction of various traits simultaneously using information across the entire genome, thus enabling higher selection intensity, including for traits that are difficult to assess phenotypically. Agroscope is currently working on implementing genomic selection within its Italian ryegrass breeding programme using a novel approach.

Fodder plant breeding has faced several new requirements and challenges in the past and will continue to do so in the future. However, with access to an increasing toolbox of selection methods, the high diversity of forage species being bred and the government's new *in-situ* conservation measures providing access to a wealth of adapted Swiss genetic resources, we have various options for addressing these challenges.

Where agriculture preserves nature: mountain forage systems between use and conservation

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Mountain grasslands in Switzerland are cultural landscapes shaped over centuries by livestock grazing. These semi-natural ecosystems host exceptionally high levels of biodiversity. However, their maintenance depends on low-input agricultural use. When grazing pressure declines in remote and marginal areas – due to the decline of animal numbers, less grazing-adapted ruminant types, decrease of labour for herding and pasture clearance, shortage of water or the increasing presence of large predators – shrubs and trees rapidly recolonize these pastures. This trend causes a continuous expansion of woody vegetation across Switzerland's mountain regions, a process that significantly alters habitat composition. Evidence shows that dense shrub encroachment leads to markedly lower plant diversity compared with open pastures, though slight increases in diversity may occur at early stages of shrub establishment.

The conservation of mountain pastures is particularly important because they deliver a wide range of ecosystem services, from forage production and carbon storage to water regulation, landscape aesthetics, and cultural values. In a recent study, we disentangled the complex relationships among key ecosystem services of mountain pastures and their environmental and management drivers, including site conditions, grazing regimes, and climatic factors. The maintenance of biodiverse mountain pastures relies on traditional, extensive management. An essential element is the availability of site-adapted livestock species and breeds: Robust, well-adapted ruminants, which are able to efficiently use heterogeneous mountain forage resources, play a central role in sustaining these multifunctional landscapes. Our findings highlight that economically viable agricultural production systems remains essential for balancing the dual objectives of biodiversity conservation and productive use in mountain grassland ecosystems.

Die Bedeutung von Grasland und Futterbau für Tiergesundheit und Tierwohl

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Die grasende Kuh ist das Marketing-Icon für tierische Lebensmittel schlechthin, auch wenn in Europa der überwiegende Teil des Rindviehs, wie aller anderen Nutztierarten auch, längst im Stall steht, und dort oft nur noch mit dem physiologischen Minimum an Raufutter gefüttert wird. In der Schweiz ist das etwas anders, was nicht zuletzt am sehr grossen Grasland-Anteil der landwirtschaftlichen Nutzfläche liegt.

Das Bild der grasenden Kuh verweist die Konsumierenden auf eine Vorstellung von Nachhaltigkeit, Tiergesundheit und Tierwohl, und das nicht zu Unrecht. Das Rind ist ein Steppentier, ein *Grazer*, perfekt daran angepasst, das tendenziell eher proteinarme Gras zu verdauen und seine tägliche Diät zu ergänzen mit den vorhandenen Kräutern, sowie Laub von Sträuchern und Bäumen. Gesundheit könnte man in diesem Kontext so definieren, dass das Tier in der Lage wäre, seinen eigenen Metabolismus durch Grasens und selektives Fressen von wirkstoffreichen Kräutern und nährstoffreichem Laub so zu balancieren und zu steuern, wie es seiner evolutionär entwickelten Physiologie entspricht. Und Tierwohl hiesse analog, dass die Kuh ihre entsprechenden Verhaltensweisen vollständig ausleben könnte.

Dies ist im landwirtschaftlichen Kontext aufgrund der Produktionsrahmenbedingungen, der Genetik und des Zugangs zu Flächen nur noch eingeschränkt möglich. Aber das eigentliche Fressverhalten und die ursprüngliche Verdauungsphysiologie könnten wieder mehr zur Grundlage einer Tierwohl- und Tiergesundheitsperspektive gemacht werden, mit dem Ziel, verhaltensbasierte Einsichten in die Tierfütterung zu bekommen und zu nutzen. Darauf basierend ist die Rolle des Graslands nicht nur eine Ressource sondern auch ein funktionales Element artgerechter Fütterung.

Ähnliche Überlegungen gelten im Übrigen auch für Geflügel und Schweine, die als Omnivoren natürlicherweise auch einen Teil Ration aus Raufutter aufnehmen.

Net human-edible protein yield and greenhouse gas emissions of grass-based dairy production

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In der Schweiz und global sind rund 70% der landwirtschaftlich genutzten Flächen mit Grasland bedeckt. Die Schweizer Milch- und Fleischproduktion beruht deshalb zu einem bedeutenden Teil auf Futter, das auf diesen nicht direkt für die menschliche Ernährung nutzbaren Flächen gewonnen wird. Zur Erhöhung der Einzeltierleistungen werden auch hierzulande in der Wiederkäuerfütterung steigende Mengen menschlich verwertbarer Futtermittel eingesetzt, die auf Ackerflächen produziert werden. Um zu evaluieren, welchen Beitrag Tierproduktionssysteme zur Nahrungsmittelversorgung leisten, werden zunehmend Konzepte angewandt, welche nicht nur den Output (Milch und Fleisch), sondern auch den Input (Futter und Flächen) berücksichtigen. So nimmt mit dem Einsatz von Futtermitteln mit höherer Energie- bzw. Proteinkonzentration (wie Kraftfutter oder Ganzpflanzenmais) auch die Konkurrenz zur menschlichen Ernährung zu – sei es direkt (über Futtermittel, die auch direkt durch den Menschen verzehrt werden könnten) oder indirekt (über die Flächen, wo die Futtermittel angebaut werden). Die Tierproduktion ist durch die zusätzliche trophische Stufe immer weniger effizient als die direkte Nutzung von Ackerprodukten für die menschliche Ernährung.

Höhere Einzeltierleistungen führen aufgrund des Verdünnungseffekts für den Erhaltungsbedarf sowie durch die höhere Verdaulichkeit bei rohfaserärmerer Fütterung hingegen zu einem tieferen CO₂-Fussabdruck pro kg Produkt. Es entsteht somit ein Zielkonflikt zwischen der Intensivierung der Produktion durch konzentriertere Rationen und der effizienten Nutzung der Ressourcen (Futter und Flächen).

Um diesen Zielkonflikt aufzulösen, schlagen wir vor, die Nettoproteinproduktion (= Protein in tierischen Produkten – menschlich verwertbares Protein in den Futtermitteln) ins Verhältnis zu den Treibhausgasemissionen zu stellen. Anhand von Betriebsdaten aus dem Ressourcenprojekt KlimaStaR Milch sehen wir, dass auf Milchviehbetrieben in der Schweiz pro kg CO₂-Äquivalent 0 - 32 g Rohprotein produziert wird. Die Menge nimmt mit zunehmendem Wiesenfutteranteil in der Fütterung zu.

Entsprechend folgern wir, dass hohe Graslandanteile in der Fütterung von Wiederkäuern besonders ressourceneffizient sind, sofern die Zielgrösse die menschliche Verwertbarkeit der eingesetzten Futtermittel mitberücksichtigt.

**Aktuelle Forschungsprojekte -
Projets de recherche actuels -
Current research projects**

Restoring alpine pastures: the impact of Highland cattle on *Alnus viridis* encroachment

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Alnus viridis is a shrub species encroaching mountain pastures in Central Europe, with negative ecological and economic consequences. Although targeted grazing with robust livestock breeds can limit shrub expansion, its effectiveness in restoring plant diversity and forage quality remains poorly documented. We evaluated the impact of Highland cattle grazing on vegetation dynamics in a summer pasture in the Swiss Alps, in the canton of Vaud. Since 2019, a herd has grazed two 7–8 ha paddocks at an average stocking rate of 0.22 LU ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, and a third paddock was included in 2020. We characterized long-term vegetation cover changes of the paddocks through manual classification of orthophotos and satellite images from multiple years. Moreover, we assessed the impact of five years of Highland cattle grazing on vegetation structure by surveying *A. viridis* shrubs and recording branch mortality, resprouting, and understory light availability in relation to cattle stocking density measured through GPS livestock tracking. Finally, we conducted botanical surveys along permanent transects in 2019 and 2024 to evaluate changes in plant species richness and pastoral value over time. After the introduction of Highland cattle, shrubland cover decreased by 4%. Higher livestock stocking density around shrubs increased branch mortality and understory light availability. The number of resprouts also increased with stocking density. Species richness increased from 25.5 to 32.2, and the pastoral value of open pastures improved from 12.9 to 17.7. Overall, our findings show that Highland cattle effectively reduce *A. viridis* cover, increase understory light availability, thereby promoting plant diversity and pastoral value of grasslands. However, the resprouting response to higher livestock density indicates that a five-year grazing period is insufficient to fully control woody encroachment. Therefore, long-term grazing management is essential to restore pastures encroached by *A. viridis*.

Selecting Study Areas Representative for the highly diverse Growth Conditions in the Swiss summering zone

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Site-specific management at appropriate stocking rates is essential to maintain ecosystem services of mountain pastures. However, there is no common agreement on what an appropriate stocking rate is. Thus, in 2022, Agroscope launched the Alpine Rangeland Observation Network to create reference values for forage production, forage quality and non-provisioning ecosystem services. We present the methodology by which we ensured that the network represents all relevant conditions of the highly heterogenous Swiss mountain pastures: We (i) mapped the distribution of mountain summer pastures at hectare-level based on Swiss land use statistics and (ii) grouped these pastures by climate region and dominant bedrock type. 14 study areas (i.e. in most cases one summer farm) were selected to cover the most important climate–bedrock combinations, and to be representative in elevation and summer precipitation to the broader climate–bedrock combination(s). Thanks to this selection process, we are able to represent almost 90% of the Swiss summering zone.

Keywords: stocking rate, mountain pastures, ecosystem services, study area selection

Multispecies mixtures enhance yield and trampling resistance

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Resistance and resilience of grasslands to disturbance is crucial in grassland-based production systems. Here, we investigated the effect of simulated trampling in a field experiment using six key forage species of temperate productive grasslands: two grasses, two legumes, and two herbs. Grassland communities were established by varying species richness and composition, and two trampling events were applied by a device simulating the pressure of adult cattle claws and treating on average 30% of the area. Total community yield was then harvested three times until the end of the growing season and compared to a non-trampling control. Six weeks after trampling, species-specific yield reductions were observed with grasses being least affected (-4%), followed by legumes (-27%) and herbs (-37%). Mixtures generally outperformed the monocultures' average, and the six-species mixture yielded more under trampling than the grass monocultures under control conditions. Nineteen weeks after trampling, at the end of the growing season, all communities recovered and no trampling effect was observed. We conclude that multispecies mixtures comprising grasses, legumes, and herbs enhance short-term yield resistance and are largely resilient to trampling events.

Formulation and testing of a nutrient solution derived from organic waste to support hydroponic lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* ‘Frilice’) production for Space applications

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Most Space agencies plan to integrate crop production into Bioregenerative Life Support Systems (BLSS) for long-duration space missions to reduce dependence on resupply from Earth. Crops contribute simultaneously to food production, water purification, oxygen regeneration and CO₂ removal. Their successful cultivation within BLSS, however, requires a reliable nutrient supply through the recycling of organic wastes. Waste streams such as urine and inedible plant residues differ widely in elemental composition, may contain nutrients in plant-unavailable forms, and can include toxic compounds. These characteristics complicate the formulation of nutrient solutions and hinder reliable crop production.

This study aimed to formulate a macronutrient-complete hydroponic solution for lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* ‘Frilice’) by optimizing the contributions of two waste-derived inputs synthetic nitrified urine and water-extracts of soybean residues, to approximate a Control solution providing all nutrients in appropriate concentrations and water-soluble ionic forms. An optimization model was developed to minimize deviations from the target nutrient composition of the Control, obtaining a Waste_mix formulation that was subsequently tested to evaluate its capacity to support lettuce yield and physiological performance. Lettuce growth, physiological traits, and tissue elemental composition were measured at harvest, while the elemental composition and dissolved organic matter (DOM) characteristics of nutrient solutions were monitored weekly.

Lettuces supplied with the Waste_mix solution exhibited markedly reduced biomass and altered tissue nutrient composition compared to those grown in the Control, despite sufficient macronutrient concentrations in the solution. UV-visible spectroscopy revealed more complex, higher molecular weight DOM in the Waste Mix solution than in the Control, originating from soybean residue extracts. These findings suggest that reduced yields in lettuces supplied with Waste_mix solution is likely driven by phytotoxicity and/or interference with

nutrient uptake caused by soybean-derived DOM, rather than by nutrient deficiency.

We conclude that it is possible to formulate a macronutrient-complete nutrient solution for lettuces in hydroponics from organic wastes, but that toxic compounds in waste-derived formulations must be mitigated before such solutions can reliably support crop production in BLSS.

Nitrogen sources used by tropical forages in the Amazon forest margins under low input management: A ^{15}N study

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The forest margins in the Colombian Amazon are a key ecosystem for dairy production for local communities. Pastures were established shortly after the first human settlements in the mid 20th century, and their nutrient management has been poor since then due to a lack of maintenance fertilization practices. Despite the soils in the region having low plant-available nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), pioneer farmers maintain productive pastures with improved *Urochloa* spp. (syn. *Brachiaria*) grasses. The objective of our study was to investigate the N sources used by *Urochloa* grasses in this soil and whether they differed between grass species (*U. humidicola* and *U. brizantha*), with the presence of a legume (*Arachis pintoii*) in the pasture, or with P fertilization. To this end, we established a repacked soil column experiment with soil from the northern Caquetá region of Colombia. Each column was filled with 50 kg of dry soil, thereby recreating a 0-50 cm profile as found in the field. For one year after the establishment of stable grass-alone and grass-legume communities, we monitored the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ signatures of plant shoots after regrowth periods of six weeks. At the middle and the end of the evaluation period, we also determined the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ composition of soil mineral N. Then, a 20% atom¹⁵N excess solution was applied to the soil to evaluate the N_2 fixation ability of grasses and the legume by analyzing the ^{15}N dilution in their shoots compared to a non- N_2 -fixing reference plant (Cyperaceae). At the end of the establishment period (3 months after seeding), the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ signature of the grass shoots was on average +0.63‰ ($\pm 1.74\%$), and became increasingly ^{15}N depleted until the fourth harvest, reaching $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ average values of -3.3‰ ($\pm 0.52\%$), regardless of the pasture composition or P treatment. The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ signatures of grass shoots changed little in the following five harvests. Preliminary results from both the ^{15}N natural abundance and ^{15}N -enriched phase of the experiment indicate the interaction of different processes involved in N uptake and use by the grasses. Associative N_2 fixation, plant internal isotopic fractionation during N assimilation, and different fates of soil ammonium- and nitrate N within the plant may play a pivotal role in *Urochloa* grasses' N nutrition.

Conservation pest control in sugar beet– a PhD project in its last steps

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Since the ban on neonicotinoid seed treatments has come into force, sugar beet production has faced major challenges, particularly due to virus yellows disease. This virus complex is primarily transmitted by the green peach aphid (*Myzus persicae*), and effective preventive control options are currently limited. Flower strips designed to promote natural enemies have therefore gained attention as a potential agroecological measure to reduce aphid populations and virus transmission at an early stage of crop development. The present project aimed to quantify the benefits and risks of different types of flowering elements in sugar beet cultivation. The research encompassed three complementary assessments: the influence of flower strip type on natural enemies, aphid density, virus incidence, and sugar yield; the species-specific attractiveness of flowering plants to *M. persicae*; and the overall suitability of micro-flower strips integrated into sugar beet production systems.

Field experiments were conducted in 2023 comparing autumn-sown annual, spring-sown annual and perennial flower strips with two types of control strips (sugar beet strips, with and without insecticide application) within sugar beet fields. Treatments were assessed for floral resource availability, abundance of natural enemies, aphid infestation, virus incidence, and sugar yield. A greenhouse choice experiment was carried out to test the attractiveness of selected flower strip plant species to *M. persicae*. In 2024, micro-flower strips sown in autumn 2023 were evaluated in a randomized block design to assess their competitiveness with sugar beet and their impact on yield.

The results showed that autumn-sown annual and perennial flower strips provided significantly earlier and more abundant floral resources than spring-sown annual flower strips. Consequently, the two previously mentioned strip types supported higher abundances of natural enemies, particularly during early-season periods that are critical for sugar beet protection. However, no negative relationship between natural enemy abundance and overall aphid populations could be observed. Fields with high aphid densities also harboured high numbers of predators, indicating that natural enemies mainly responded secondarily to aphid

outbreaks. Regarding *M. persicae* specifically, less individuals were found close to perennial flower strips but no relationship with natural enemy density was detected. Virus incidence was primarily influenced by the sowing date of sugar beets, landscape structure, weather conditions between 20 April and 27 June, and total *M. persicae* density in sugar beet fields. No consistent effect of flower strip type on virus incidence could be demonstrated.

In the greenhouse choice experiment, *Vicia sativa*, *Trifolium pratense*, *Anethum graveolens*, *Achillea millefolium* and *Fagopyrum esculentum* were significantly less attractive to *M. persicae* than sugar beet, suggesting their potential use as repellent or diversionary companion plants in in-field measures such as micro-flower strips.

The establishment of micro-flower strips within sugar beet fields required technical adjustments, which were successfully implemented by modifying existing machinery. One micro-flower strip mixture showed no significant yield reduction compared to control plots, indicating promising options for practical implementation. The treatment that did not result in a significant yield reduction included *Anthriscus cerefolium*, *Avena strigosa*, and *Trigonella foenum-graecum*.

Overall, this project demonstrates that flower strips in sugar beet cultivation provide clear ecological benefits by supplying early floral resources and enhancing populations of natural enemies. However, their contribution to the preventive control of aphids and virus transmission in sugar beet remains limited, at least in the study year. Flower strip effectiveness strongly depends on sowing time and plant species composition. Micro-flower strips sown across the entire field and composed of plant species unattractive to *M. persicae* represent a promising complement to conventional flower strips, but they require further optimization and field evaluation.

Impacts of organic fertilisation strategies on grassland soil organic carbon stocks: A case-study from Grisons

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Grasslands are an important element of agriculture in the canton of Grisons and store substantial amounts of soil organic carbon (SOC), making them central to both agricultural production and climate change mitigation. Organic fertilisation plays a key role in this context, linking management with SOC dynamics and greenhouse gas (GHG) fluxes, which highlights the need to understand its long-term impacts on SOC stocks.

This study used the Rothamsted Carbon (RothC) model (Coleman et al., 1997; parametrised following Wüst-Galley et al., 2020; Keel et al., 2025) to simulate SOC dynamics in permanent grasslands in Grisons until 2050. Model input data, SOC measurements and fertilisation records (2020-2023), were collected from farms participating in the project *climate-neutral agriculture in Grisons*. Thereby, the farms were clustered into two farm types according to elevation and livestock density: Within each cluster, three levels of initial SOC stocks (minimum, median and maximum), and fertilisation intensities (minimum, median and maximum amounts of organic carbon (C_{org}) applied) were chosen to represent the variation of current conditions under a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. This was contrasted with two scenarios in which the application of composted manure and anaerobically fermented slurry were simulated.

Model results indicated that initial SOC stocks were pivotal in shaping future trajectories: Across both clusters, grasslands with low or median initial SOC stocks showed potential for stabilisation or increases, while high initial SOC stocks tended to decline (Figure 1). These trends were consistent across the BAU, compost and fermented slurry scenarios, and are in line with measured long-term changes in other studies (Wiesmeier et al., 2025). This reflects the difficulty of maintaining high SOC stocks, which in the past have been favoured by stabilising factors such as cool, wet climate, but may in the future be particularly at risk from climate change-induced changes in precipitation and temperature patterns (Wiesmeier et al., 2025). However, increasing C_{org} inputs through fertilisation to compensate for this decline would increase the risk of nitrogen surpluses and subsequent losses to the environment. An alternative way of maintaining or increasing SOC stocks is through the choice of organic fertilisers. Applying compost tended to reduce SOC stock decreases at high

initial SOC stock levels and led to higher SOC stock increases at low and median initial SOC stocks compared to the BAU scenario. This occurred despite lower C_{org} inputs due to carbon losses during composting (Keel et al., 2025). However, the lower nitrogen availability in compost compared with manure may limit productivity in the short-term. Contrastingly, anaerobically fermented slurry showed no potential to stabilise or increase SOC stocks, but would provide immediately higher nitrogen availability due to a larger proportion of ammonium.

These findings emphasize the importance of initial SOC stocks as site-specific determinants for the potential of future stock increases. Nevertheless, the results indicate that management choices can influence SOC dynamics, but balancing productivity with SOC stock stabilisation or increases for climate change mitigation remains essential.

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Bastard-Raigras verbessert die botanische Qualität von Gras-Klee-Mischungen

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Im Futterbau gemässigter Klimazonen spielen die ertragreichen Raigräser (*Lolium* spp.) eine wichtige Rolle. Insbesondere ihre Futterqualität wird geschätzt. Das Englische Raigras (*Lolium perenne* L.) ist eine wertvolle Futterpflanzenart, die in vielen Futterbaumischungen für drei und mehr Jahre ihre Anwendung findet. Unter Mähnutzung wird diese Art jedoch sehr bald im Pflanzenbestand durch andere, nicht gleichermassen hochwertige, aber ausdauerndere Gräser der Mischung abgelöst.

In einem dreijährigen Experiment wurde der Effekt eines teilweisen Ersatzes des Englischen Raigrases in der Samenmischung durch Bastard-Raigras (*Lolium x hybridum* Hausskn.) des dem Englischen Raigras ähnlichen ER-Typs untersucht. Die botanische Zusammensetzung und der Trockensubstanzertrag von vier Mischungen mit Knaulgras (*Dactylis glomerata* L.), Wiesenschwingel (*Festuca pratensis* Hudson.), Timothe (*Phleum pratense* L.), Rotklee (*Trifolium pratense* L.) und Weissklee (*Trifolium repens* L.), die entweder nur Englisches Raigras oder Englisches Raigras und Bastard-Raigras des ER-Typs enthielten, wurden im ersten Aufwuchs des ersten und zweiten Hauptnutzungsjahres beurteilt. Während des beobachteten Zeitraumes erhöhte die Zugabe von Bastard-Raigras den Gesamt-Raigrasanteil um das 1.47fache auf 46 %. Gleichzeitig reduzierte das Bastard-Raigras den Anteil an Nicht-Raigräsern um etwa 30 %. Während das Bastard-Raigras den Kleeanteil im ersten Aufwuchs des ersten Hauptnutzungsjahres um 33 % verminderte, hatte es im ersten Aufwuchs des zweiten Hauptnutzungsjahres keinen weiteren Einfluss darauf. Hinsichtlich des Ertrags hatte die Verwendung von Bastard-Raigras weder im jeweiligen ersten Aufwuchs beider Hauptnutzungsjahre noch gesamthaft in den Jahreserträgen eine Bedeutung.

Der Gewinn des Einsatzes von Bastard-Raigras liegt bei einer Erhöhung des Raigrasanteils, nicht des Ertrags. Die Beigabe von Bastard-Raigras des ER-Typs verbessert die botanische Qualität von dreijährigen Gras-Klee-Mischungen, die Englisches Raigras enthalten, deutlich.

Can soil amendments improve phosphorus (P) use efficiency of crops grown on oxidized acid sulfate soils with contrasting soil P availability?

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Acid sulfate soils (ASS) cover large areas both in Vietnam and globally. When oxidized, these soils have very low pH, high exchangeable aluminum (Al), and low P availability. P availability in the agricultural oxidized topsoils in the Vietnamese Mekong Delta varies greatly, ranging from very low to very high values; the latter may be due to high P fertilizer application rates (Pham et al. 2020). This most likely leads to low P use efficiency (PUE) in crops. The objective of our study was to evaluate whether soil amendments that potentially enhance soil P availability, microbial P recycling, and soil pH can improve crop PUE in soils with contrasting P availability.

Our experiments involved two topsoils: one with high water-extractable P (P_{water} , 12.8 mg P kg⁻¹ soil) and another with P_{water} below the detection limit, referred to as HiP and LoP soil, respectively. The amendments tested included lime, biochar, farmyard manure compost, and Ca-ash (ashed sewage sludge treated with CaCl₂ at 1,100°C), representing different application P rates. Water-soluble phosphorus (WSP, added at 50 mg P kg⁻¹ soil) and no P addition (No P) served as positive and negative controls, respectively. In the pot experiment with LoP soil only, three additional treatments were included: combinations of lime, biochar, or compost with WSP, with each amendment applied at the same rate as in the individual treatments. Two types of experiments were conducted: a pot experiment with common bent grass (*Agrostis capillaris* var Barking), and a soil incubation experiment without plants. Soil available P of HiP and LoP soils was labeled with ³³PO₄³⁻ before amendments addition. The incubation experiment included five destructive samplings, and the pot experiment involved four grass shoot cuts.

Our pot experiment results showed, for total dry grass shoot biomass or total shoot P (TSP) content, that there were no significant differences among treatments in HiP soil; however, in LoP soil, the values of both parameters were higher in the treatments involving application of Ca-ash or WSP compared to No P. Compost alone increased only the TSP, with no significant effects on biomass compared to

No P. Among P-amended treatments (i.e., those involving compost, Ca-ash, and WSP), apparent PUE in HiP soil ranged from 0.9 to 4.3% and did not differ significantly across treatments. In contrast, in LoP soil, the apparent PUE of the compost treatment (9.6%) was significantly lower than that of all other treatments (14.0 – 18.1%), except compost combined with WSP (13.1%).

The incubation experiment revealed that at day 82 of incubation (end of the experiment), both resin extractable P (available P) and the soil's isotopically exchangeable P measured on an anion exchange resin membrane (potentially available P) did not differ significantly across treatments in HiP soil. However, the figures were higher in the compost, Ca-ash, and WSP treatments than in the other treatments. These data patterns are the same for the grass's total shoot P in the two soils, implying the response of the grass's shoot P uptake to the soil P availability. The recovery of ^{33}P by soil microbes was negligible, with a maximum of $<7 \text{ KBq g}^{-1}$ soil at day 15 of incubation, and became $\sim 0 \text{ KBq g}^{-1}$ soil since day 35 of incubation (the radioactivity was back-calculated to soil labelling day). Soil pH, however, was not significantly affected by any treatment and did not significantly change over time.

The very low apparent PUE observed in the HiP soil was due to the already high level of plant-available phosphorus, which was sufficient to meet plant P demand and support growth. In this soil, the added phosphorus, which was largely diluted within the existing soil P pool, did not substantially increase P availability. In contrast, in the LoP soil with low initial P availability, amendments such as Ca-ash, WSP, and compost significantly increased soil P availability, thereby enhancing plant growth and/or phosphorus uptake. Consequently, the apparent PUE of the grass in LoP soil was much higher than in HiP soil. Amendments such as lime and biochar did not improve soil pH, likely due to the soil's high pH buffer capacity. Negligible recovery of ^{33}P by soil microbes suggests that microbial activity did not play an important role in P cycling or in determining PUE. Overall, the higher PUE observed in LoP soil compared to HiP soil appears to be primarily due to the increased plant-available phosphorus contributed by the amendments, rather than to changes in the soil's chemical or biological properties induced by them. In conclusion, for acid sulfate soils (ASS) with high P availability like the HiP soil, P fertilizer application is unnecessary. Conversely, for ASS with low P availability like the LoP soil, phosphorus fertilization is needed to increase P availability, enhance plant growth and uptake, and ultimately improve PUE.

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Improving the improvement program: Optimizing fodder plant breeding strategies with stochastic simulations

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Plant breeding programs are inherently complex, requiring breeders to make strategic decisions to allocate the often limited resources efficiently. Recent advances in genomic selection (GS), high-throughput phenotyping and rapid generation advance offer substantial potential to accelerate genetic gain. However, the successful integration of such methods into breeding programs remains an active area of research, as their impact depends strongly on species biology and breeding program structure. In this context, computer simulations offer a rapid, and cost-effective way to evaluate how these tools can be incorporated into breeding. This project aims to identify opportunities to increase genetic gain in Agroscope's fodder plant breeding program by optimizing breeding schemes through simulation-based methods. To this end, we first characterized the crossing, evaluation and selection decisions underlying the Italian ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum* Lam.) breeding pipeline. Using this information, we developed a simplified digital twin of the breeding strategy and simulated the trends of genetic gain over the past 30 years. These trends defined the baseline scenario and form the basis for simulating alternative strategies. Building on this baseline, we evaluated scenarios incorporating GS on single plants with a testcross to allow progeny testing, and reduced cycle length approaches, focusing on their effect to change genetic gain trends over the next 50 years. Our results highlight avenues for implementing GS and shorten breeding cycles, both of which can advance genetic gain and improve the breeding program. These strategies represent viable pathways towards developing higher-yielding, more nutritious and resilient fodder plants for the future.

Extensification des prairies de montagne – entre rendement et biodiversité

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Les prairies de fauche de montagne revêtent une grande valeur économique, écologique et culturelle pour les régions alpines. Elles sont aujourd'hui menacées à la fois par l'abandon des terres dans les zones reculées et par l'intensification des pratiques agricoles, en particulier via l'ajout de fertilisants permettant d'augmenter les rendements dans les zones favorables. Ces deux modifications des pratiques agricoles ont des répercussions négatives sur la flore et la faune. Dans cette étude répliquée sur douze sites, nous avons expérimentalement extensifié les pratiques agricoles dans deux des trois prairies sélectionnées par site, soit par une réduction à un tiers de l'apport initial de fertilisants (prairie dite peu-intensive), soit par l'arrêt complet de la fertilisation (prairie dite extensive). Les prairies concernées étaient gérées de manière intensive depuis au moins 20 ans. Cinq ans après l'arrêt de la fertilisation, le nombre d'espèces végétales est significativement plus élevé de 18.4 % dans les prairies extensives que dans les prairies restées intensives (prairies témoins), notamment en raison d'un plus grand nombre de légumineuses et de plantes herbacées. De plus, la réduction et l'arrêt de la fertilisation entraîne une diminution de la densité végétale, se traduisant par une baisse conséquente du rendement de la première fauche annuelle de -32.2 % et -15.3 % respectivement. En terme de qualité du fourrage, les prairies extensives présentent une teneur en protéines supérieure dans le fourrage de première fauche par rapport aux prairies témoins, sans différence significative pour la digestibilité (ADF, NDF, ADL) ni pour les valeurs énergétiques (NEL, NEV). Les différences de rendement et de qualité pour la deuxième fauche ne sont pas significatives. Ces résultats indiquent que, pour une gestion durable et viable à long terme, il est important de maintenir une gestion hétérogène des prairies de montagne afin de concilier rendement agricole et biodiversité.

Biodiversity payments sustain grassland plant diversity, whereas abandonment leads to loss

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European grasslands rank among the most species-rich ecosystems worldwide, supporting exceptional biodiversity and vital ecosystem services. Yet, these habitats are increasingly threatened by land-use intensification on one side and abandonment on the other. Since the early 1990s, Switzerland and other European countries have implemented agri-environmental schemes to conserve grassland biodiversity, ecosystem functions, and cultural values. We evaluated long-term vegetation change in the Swiss Alps to test the effectiveness of these measures for biodiversity conservation. We resurveyed more than 300 vegetation plots in the montane to subalpine belt (600–2000 m a.s.l.) across the Swiss Alps, drawing on multiple historical datasets. Sites were selected using a stratified design across municipalities to cover the full gradient of management intensity and trajectories. Changes in species richness were quantified with models accounting for observer error, and shifts in community composition and mean ecological indicator values were analyzed. Biodiversity trends varied markedly among management regimes based on the agri-environmental schemes. The strongest gains in richness were observed under result-based payments (BFF QII). Management-based payments (BFF QI) and conventional management did not show a change in richness. The most pronounced declines occurred in abandoned plots, which also exhibited marked shifts in community composition. Our findings provide clear evidence that result-based payments are effective in maintaining and enhancing plant diversity in montane to subalpine grasslands. At the same time, abandonment poses a major threat, emphasizing the need for sustained conservation policies and targeted management to safeguard grassland biodiversity under changing land-use and climatic conditions.

Genetic diversity monitoring: unravelling dynamics of species and cultivar compositions in grassland

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Temporary grasslands are key components of sustainable ruminant production and integrated crop-livestock systems. Mixtures of grass and legume seeds for temporary grasslands commonly consist of multiple species, often represented by different cultivars. The species composition temporally changes according to the substitution principle: Fast-growing species dominate early on, while slower-growing species gradually take over. Shifts in species and cultivar compositions are essential for long-term stability and productivity of swards and are of ecological and agronomical interest. While species composition can be monitored through visual assessment and botanical surveys, shifts in cultivar compositions cannot be detected visually and require different approaches. Molecular genetic methods can be used to assess plant genetic diversity (PGD) and measure these shifts. Two common methods used to analyse PGD are multispecies amplicon sequencing (MSAS) and genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS). While MSAS targets conserved sequences among species, GBS is a reduced genome representation method. Despite the potential of these methods, studies monitoring PGD are scarce due to difficulties in taking representative samples and lack of standardised and affordable indicators of PGD. In this study, we successfully applied MSAS and GBS to assess PGD of agronomically relevant grassland species and detect shifts in cultivar compositions. Using MSAS on samples containing pools of five species, we could taxonomically separate all the species (*Dactylis glomerata* L., *Festuca pratensis* Huds., *Lolium perenne* L., *Trifolium pratense* L., *T. repens* L.). Additionally, we could differentiate accessions within species with fixation index (F_{ST}) values ranging from 0.014 for *T. repens* to 0.089 for *L. perenne*. To assess further applications of MSAS, we simulated shifts in cultivar compositions that could occur in practice under field conditions. Based on an extended *L. perenne* sample set of six cultivars grown in a greenhouse, pure and mixed samples containing one and two cultivars, respectively, were prepared and analysed using

MSAS and GBS. For the mixtures, cultivars were pooled at two different ratios, 50:50 and 75:25, based on length of leaf fragments. For both MSAS and GBS, the 50:50-ratio mixtures separated from the corresponding cultivars according to this ratio. Furthermore, GBS allowed for separation of 75:25-ratio mixtures from the corresponding cultivars and 50:50-ratio mixtures. These results indicate complementing applications in PGD monitoring of the two approaches. While we anticipate that MSAS with its cost-effectiveness could be applied to largescale and long-term PGD monitoring of multispecies grasslands, GBS with its lower detection limit could be applied to studies where cultivar composition shifts are of interest.

From Sequence to Cross-Compatibility Prediction: A Functional Analysis of Self-Incompatibility Haplotypes in Forage Grasses

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Hybrid breeding forms the basis of seed production for many crop species. In forage grasses, however, self-pollination and inbred line production are naturally prevented by gametophytic self-incompatibility (SI), a genetic mechanism that promotes outcrossing. In grasses, SI is controlled by two multi-allelic loci, *S* and *Z*. At each locus, three genes are involved in self-recognition: two genes encoding a transmembrane protein (DUF247) expressed in the pollen, and one gene encoding a small, secreted peptide expressed in the stigma. Yet, knowledge of their sequence diversity, allelic variation and physiological functions remains limited. Understanding how these genes interact to regulate SI could unlock opportunities to control pollination and support the development of hybrid breeding strategies.

To build a model predicting cross-compatibility based on genotypic data, we established an F₁ population of perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.), derived from a polycross of five parental plants. Consequently, the population comprises a restricted number of haplotypes at the two SI loci *S* and *Z*. To identify the different SI alleles present within the population, we used a probe capture assay, followed by next-generation sequencing and *de novo* assembly of alleles. Based on the translated amino acid sequence, we clustered the different SI alleles with 99% similarity to form putative SI haplotypes. To link the genotypic data to phenotypic data from semi-*in vivo* pollination assays, we performed more than 2,900 targeted crosses between 30 plants within the F₁ population in 2023 and 2024: an example semi-*in vivo* pollination is shown in Figure 1. Currently, we are repeating the crosses for a subset of ten genotypes, for which we were able to fully recover the putative SI haplotypes at both loci. This fully characterized subset was used to train a model for cross-compatibility predictions. We were able to assess the overlap between the predicted cross-compatibility and the observed cross-compatibility in the 2023 crosses. In 30 out of 58 crosses, the predicted and observed cross-compatibility was identical. However, twelve crosses deviated by

at least 50% in observed cross-compatibilities. By analyzing the phenotypic data from 2024 and 2025, we seek to better understand the sources of variation between the predicted and observed cross-compatibility.

Ultimately, we aim to define which sequence characteristics of the SI alleles determine SI recognition, with a view to defining functional haplotypes. This knowledge would enable the development of a tool for breeders to assess the allelic diversity of SI in their breeding pool and to predict cross-compatibility between genotypes.

Symactiv Pellets: A biostimulant in which biology is the main driver of soil health.

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The pressure on the food sector is increasing: with a growing population and environmental challenges, building a sustainable and healthy crop sector is an utmost priority. Currently, most farmers rely on chemical fertilizers and pesticides to increase crop yields and protect crops. Nevertheless, these chemicals are costly and have broad negative environmental impacts. In particular, every day we lose hundreds of thousands of hectares of soil due to agricultural practices. At this rate, most of our agricultural land would be degraded by 2050, affecting food production for billions of people. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop new agricultural amendments that are both safe and effective.

At Symactiv, we aim to regenerate soil with a chemical-free fertilizer to help farmers increase their yields. We developed a microbial-enriched Swiss pellet. Our results show increased yields across crops, improved plant resilience, and enhanced nutrient uptake, particularly phosphorus and calcium, following Symactiv pellet use. In our trials, we also observed a 20% increase in water retention. The rhizosphere microbiome diversity analysis of treated crops shows that Symactiv pellets are a major driver of the fungal community structure in the soil. These results position our pellet as a safe and effective fertilizer to strengthen the Swiss agricultural sector.

Quelle fréquence optimale de prairies temporaires dans la rotation pour maintenir la qualité des sols agricoles ?

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La matière organique du sol (MOS) est fondamentale pour maintenir des sols de bonne qualité soutenant la production végétale. L'assolement a un impact important sur la teneur en MOS. Celle-ci est typiquement plus élevée dans les prairies permanentes que dans les terres arables. L'intégration de prairies temporaires dans la rotation des cultures est une pratique efficace pour limiter la perte de MOS dans les terres arables. Néanmoins, les prairies temporaires peuvent être considérées comme concurrentes de la production alimentaire destinée à la consommation humaine, car elles produisent du fourrage pour nourrir le bétail. Dans un contexte de spécialisation de la production agricole et de dégradation des sols, il est impératif d'évaluer l'impact sur la teneur en MOS d'une diminution des prairies temporaires et de leur fréquence dans les rotations culturales. De plus, il est essentiel d'évaluer s'il existe une fréquence optimale de prairies temporaires dans la rotation permettant de minimiser une concurrence entre production alimentaire destinée à la consommation humaine et la perte de qualité des sols.

Pour répondre à ces questions, nous avons utilisé le Réseau d'observation des sols du Canton de Fribourg (FRIBO) pour évaluer la relation entre la fréquence des prairies temporaires, le niveau de MOS et la qualité des sols. La dynamique du carbone organique (COS) dans les 20 premiers cm du sol des 250 sites du réseau a été estimée grâce aux prélèvements réalisés tous les cinq ans pendant 30 ans. De plus, les stocks de COS ont été mesurés jusqu'à une profondeur de 50 cm dans une sélection des sites. Les prairies permanentes ont été utilisées comme référence pour estimer la perte de MOS, en contrôlant les variations entre les parcelles des caractéristiques du sol (par exemple, l'argile et le pH) et du site (par exemple, l'altitude, les précipitations et le type de cultures).

Les résultats montrent une perte de MOS dans les terres assolées dépendante de la fréquence de prairies temporaires dans la rotation. Cette relation étant linéaire, elle ne permet pas de définir un optimum basé sur un point de bascule à partir duquel la perte de MOS serait plus importante. L'optimum a donc été défini en fonction d'un niveau de MOS au-delà duquel la qualité du sol n'est plus jugée suffisante pour en assurer ses fonctions. Il se base sur le ratio COS : argile de 1/10 qui permet une structuration du sol satisfaisante selon l'Évaluation Visuelle de la Structure du Sol (VESS).

Cette étude a permis d'identifier une fréquence de prairies temporaires optimale afin de maintenir un niveau de qualité des sols minimisant l'impact négatif sur leur fonctionnement. Ce seuil est toutefois valide avec des pratiques agricoles conventionnelles. Les résultats montrent qu'il est aussi possible d'atteindre le

ratio COS : argile cible sans prairies temporaires. Cela souligne l'importance et l'efficacité de mettre en place d'autres pratiques favorisant la MOS en absence de prairie temporaires dans la rotation de cultures.

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